

Enhanced production of L-threonine by an α,ϵ -diamopimilic acid and thiamine-HCl dual auxotrophic mutant *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870

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A high yielding L-threonine auxotrophic mutant *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 was developed by induced mutation using UV irradiations as a physical mutagen followed by penicillin selection. It was an α,ϵ -diamopimilic acid (DAP) deficient mutant. Production of L-threonine was greatly influenced by thiamine-HCl (60 μ g/L) and DAP (60 mg/L) in the synthetic medium with D-glucose as a carbon source at 30°C after 72 h of incubation. The production of L-threonine was increased to 10.7 mg/ml compared to the control (0.8 mg/ml L-threonine without any supplementation) on addition of soybean extract (3%), corn-steep liquor (2%), beef extract (2%), malt extract (4%), meat extract (2%), peptone (2%) and potato scale extract (1%) in the fermentation medium.

Keywords: *Corynebacterium glutamicum*, UV irradiations, α,ϵ -diamopimilic acid, L-threonine.

Introduction

Large scale production of L-amino acids by fermentation has been started in 1957 by Japanese scientist S. Kinoshita at Kyowa Hakko Kogyo Co. through the isolation of soil bacterium *Micrococcus glutamicus* (later renamed as *Corynebacterium glutamicum*) that accumulated large amount of L-glutamic acid¹. It was a member of *Actinobacteria* and the most effective L-amino acid producer. Later on, several bacterial strains have been isolated and tested for L-amino acid production²⁻⁶.

An auxotrophic mutant is a microorganism that has additional nutrient requirements compared with its parent strain. Huang (1965) examined the dual auxotrophic nature of the *Escherichia coli* mutants for both α,ϵ -diamopimilic acid and L-methionine⁷. Takahashi *et al.* (1965) studied the effect of corn steep liquor and thiamine-HCl on L-glutamic acid production by the bacterial strain *Corynebacterium glutamicum* S10B1⁸. Hockney and Scott (1979) developed vitamin B₆ auxotrophic mutants of *Escherichia coli* K12⁹. Cassiolato and Melo (1999) used filtration enrichment method for isolation and characterization of auxotrophic mutants of *Trichoderma*

*harzianum*¹⁰. Mahmood (2015) examined the effect of different complex nutrients on L-lysine fermentation by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* FRL no. 61989¹¹. Very recently, Gavrilova *et al.* (2017) identified and characterized the spontaneous auxotrophic mutants of *Fusarium langsethiae*¹².

The principal aim of this study was to determine the auxotrophic nature of a newly developed mutant *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870. Furthermore, we intended to evaluate the potency of the mutant to utilize different indigenous raw materials available in our country as cheap sources of complex nutrients to minimize the production cost.

Materials and methods:

Microorganism: A high L-threonine yielding auxotrophic mutant *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 was developed by induced mutation using UV as mutagen followed by penicillin selection from the wild strain *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X37 which accumulated only 0.8 mg/ml L-threonine in the fermentation broth¹⁰.

Preparation of inoculum: A full grown slant of 48 h old of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 was scrapped off and

suspended in 100 ml sterile water. The cell suspension of 3% (v/v) of the seed culture (2×10^6 cells/ml) was used as inoculum.

Mutagenic treatments: 2 ml bacterial suspensions were taken in a petridish (5 cm diameter) and exposed to UV irradiations under a Hanovia germicidal lamp (15 Watt), XG-LYQ17H from a distance of 12 cm for different time intervals (10–60 min). The treated cells (mutants) were incubated at 30°C for 48 h and stored at 4°C¹⁰.

Penicillin selection of the mutants: The suitable mutant for the production of L-threonine has been selected against penicillin selection from multiple mutants developed by random UV induced mutagenesis¹¹.

Growth medium: The growth medium consisted of for the microorganism before mutagenic treatments contained: glucose, 1%; urea, 0.8%; beef extract, 0.3%; yeast extract, 0.2%; $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, 0.002%; water, 1 L and the pH of the medium was adjusted to 7.0.

Basal salt medium: The composition of the basal salt medium was: glucose, 10%; urea, 1%; KH_2PO_4 , 0.1%; K_2HPO_4 , 0.1%; $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, 0.02%; L-thiamine, 10 µg/ml; water, 1 L and the pH was adjusted to 7.0.

Addition of thiamine-HCl and α, ϵ -diaminopimilic acid: Thiamine-HCl and α, ϵ -diaminopimilic acid were added to the sterile growth medium directly from the stalk solutions under sterile conditions.

Preparation and formulation of complex nutrients:

(a) Preparation of rice bran extract and wheat bran extract: 50 g of each material was taken into 500 ml Erlenmeyer conical flask containing 250 ml warm distilled water. The suspension was kept for 48 h. The extracts were filtered separately through cotton and evaporated to dryness to recover solid content.

(b) Preparation of paddy soak liquor: 150 g of paddy was added to 250 ml distilled water and kept it at room temperature for 48 h. The extract was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover solid content.

(c) Preparation of corn steep liquor: 150 g of corn was taken into 500 ml Erlenmeyer conical flask contained 300 ml water and kept it at room temperature for 48 h. The extract was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover solid content.

(d) Preparation of soybean extract: 100 g of soybean was poured into a 500 ml Erlenmeyer conical flask contained 250 ml water and allowed to swallow for 48 h at room temperature. The soak water was extracted thoroughly and filtered through cotton. It was then dried for the determination of solid content.

All the above mentioned complex nutrients were added to the production medium according to their solid content in a sterile conditions, but beef extract, malt extract, meat extract, peptone and cane molasses were added directly to the synthetic medium. The effect of varying concentrations (1–8%) of each of the complex nutrient was examined on L-threonine production and the bacterial growth.

Detection and quantification of L-threonine: L-Threonine in the fermentation broth was assayed by ninhydrin method after separation using paper chromatography. The solvent system was composed of n-butanol:acetic acid:water (2:1:1). The spots were visualized by spraying 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone and quantitative estimation of L-threonine was done using colorimetric method¹².

Estimation of dry cell weight: After centrifugation, the bacterial precipitate was washed with double distilled, deionized water and dried at 100°C to attain a constant dry cell weight¹³.

Statistical analysis: All data were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n = 6. The data were analyzed by One Way ANOVA followed by Dunett's post hoc multiple comparison test using 'Prism 4.0' software (Graph pad Inc., USA). A 'p' value 0.05 was considered as significant and 0.001 was taken as highly significant statistically.

All the chemicals used in this study were of analytical reagent (AR) grade and were obtained from Merck. Borosil glass goods and triple distilled water were used throughout the study.

Results

Fermentation of L-threonine was carried out in a basal salt medium containing glucose as a carbon and $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ as a nitrogen sources respectively for *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 at 30°C. Maximum production of L-threonine was visible in 72 h of incubation attaining saturation followed by a gradual decline. It was probably because, the microorganism utilized/thiamine for its growth and metabolism. However depletion of thiamine-HCl, reduced the pro-

duction sharply with time. The fermentation broth containing no α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid manifested almost total inhibition of L-threonine production, suggesting thereby the newly developed mutant was a dual (thiamine-HCl and α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid) auxotroph. Fig. 1 showed the production was maximally obtained with L-threonine, 60 $\mu\text{g/L}$ on 72 h of incubation. Similarly, Fig. 2 depicted maximum productivity was obtained with α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid, 60 mg/L after the same period of incubation. In each case, both these compounds potentiated the production of L-threonine at a specific level above which inhibition of the production was evident. But bacterial growth was promoted with the graded addition of thiamine-HCl albeit excess addition of α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid in the fermentation broth led to the inhibition of bacterial growth.

Fig. 1. Determination of thiamine-HCl auxotrophic nature of the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* 1870 (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n = 6).

Fig. 2. Determination of α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid auxotrophic nature of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n = 6).

Among the complex nutrients studied, soybean extract, 3%; corn-steep liquor, 2%; beef extract, 2%, malt extract, 4%; meat extract, 2%; peptone, 2% and potato scale extract, 1% enhanced the production (Figs. 3–6). The productivity and cellular growth followed similar trend (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) in all the cases except for the soybean extract which exhibited similarity with Fig. 2.

Fig. 3. Effect of soybean extract on L-threonine production and cellular growth of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n = 6).

Fig. 4. Effect of corn steep liquor on L-threonine production and cellular growth of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n = 6).

Rice bran extract, paddy soak liquor, wheat bran extract and cane molasses showed almost no effect on the production.

Fig. 5. Effect of beef extract on L-threonine production and cellular growth of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n = 6).

Fig. 8. Effect of peptone on L-threonine production and cellular growth of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n = 6).

Fig. 6. Effect of malt extract on L-threonine production and cellular growth of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n = 6).

Fig. 9. Effect of potato scale extract on L-threonine production and cellular growth of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n = 6).

Fig. 7. Effect of meat extract on L-threonine production and cellular growth of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n = 6).

Discussion

Utilization of various low cost carbon or nitrogen sources as well as supplementation of different vitamins in the fermentation media is a common practice used since ancient past to increase the productivity. In this regard, microorganisms play a pivotal role to facilitate the production. In the present study, effect of various low cost media on the optimization of L-threonine production has been tested. From past literature, a handful information on the production of L-threonine by a number of bacterial species has been cited. L-Threonine accumulation by *Escherichia coli* 1371 in a synthetic medium using mannitol as a carbon source at 37°C was greatly altered by α, ϵ -diaminopimelic acid. The maximum production (1.5 mg/ml) was obtained after 28 h of incubation.

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However sorbitol was proved to be the best source of carbon for L-threonine production by the mutant *Escherichia coli* 13070 at 28°C in presence of both α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid and L-methionine. The maximum yield of L-threonine was obtained up to 2 mg/ml after 48 h of incubation. Addition of beet molasses or sucrose with corn steep liquor led to further improvement in the production⁷. Takahashi *et al.* (1965) studied the effects of different complex nutrients such as corn steep liquor, peptone, meat extract, and yeast extract *etc.* on L-glutamic acid production by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* S10B1. Corn steep liquor and meat extract were proved to be potential stimuli for L-glutamic acid production. Furthermore, addition of thiamine-HCl (5 g/L) in the culture medium in absence of corn steep liquor led to identical production. It revealed that the factor in corn steep liquor that potentially stimulated the production was thiamine-HCl⁸. Hockey isolated approximately 500 vitamin B₆ auxotrophic mutants from 18 independent cultures of *Escherichia coli* CR63 (Ref). They reported none of these strains grew in a minimal salt medium containing 2'-hydroxypyridoxine⁹. The effects of yeast extract, peptone, meat extract, corn steep liquor *etc.* on L-lysine production were investigated by Mahmood (2015). He also reported these complex nutrients might be good sources of nutrients for *Corynebacterium glutamicum* FRL no. 61989¹¹. Gavrilova *et al.* (2017) analyzed the auxotrophic nature of 49 strains of *Fusarium langsethiae* isolated from Northern Europe and reported that these isolates reflected natural intra-species biodiversity¹².

Conclusion

In the present study, it has been found that the newly developed mutant *Corynebacterium glutamicum* X1870 was an α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid and thiamine-HCl dual auxotrophic mutant which could utilize soybean extract, corn steep liquor, beef extract, malt extract, meat extract, peptone and potato scale extract as cheap sources of nutrients for L-threonine production. The production was increased significantly ($p < 0.001$) from 0.03 to 10.7 mg/L when the fermentation broth was supplemented with thiamine-HCl, 60 μ g/L; α,ϵ -diaminopimilic acid, 60 mg/ml; soybean extract, 3%; corn steep liquor, 2%; beef extract, 2%, malt extract, 4%; meat

extract, 2%; peptone, 2% and potato scale extract, 1%. Thus, it can be tentatively concluded that different indigenous raw materials available in our country as the cheap sources of complex nutrients were proved to be fruitful for the production of L-threonine by this mutant to reduce production cost.

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